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Figure 1. Infrastructure on ending gender-based violence, extracted from GENDERACTIONplus D3.2, p 12.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AC	Associated Countries
CoC	Code of Conduct
CoP	Community of Practice
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ERC	European Research Council
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GRC	Global Research Council
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
MLW	Mutual Learning Workshop
MS	EU Member States
NIP	National Impact Plan
NSF	National Science Foundation
PI	Principal Investigator
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
R&I	Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package
ZTA	Zero-Tolerance Approach

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of the deliverable is to develop a template for a zero-tolerance approach to gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in research funding organisations in the European Research Area. The deliverable is based on the results and recommendations from the GENDERACTIONplus D3.1 and D3.2. A continuous engagement with the GENDERACTIONplus research funding organisations, through a community of practice and a mutual learning workshop in September 2023, has been instrumental for the logic and structure of D3.3. Further, relevant position papers, policy development and tools from the UniSAFE project have informed the content development. Finally, D3.3 is aligned with the upcoming zero-tolerance approach code of conduct in the European Research Area on ending gender-based violence, and with the recently launched GenderSAFE project and its ongoing work on policy development and awareness raising. The template is a step-by-step approach for research funding organisations to end gender-based violence in research. The logic and structure of the template combine the three pillars of the code of conduct – commitment, action, and accountability – and a specific model for internal change management in research funding organisations.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. About the project

Building on the Horizon 2020 project GENDERACTION, the overall goal of GENDERACTIONplus is to contribute to the coordination of the gender equality (GE) and inclusiveness objectives of the new ERA (European Research Area) through the development of two communities of practice (CoPs), one consisting of representatives of national authorities and the second consisting of representatives of RFOs. The network is made up of a total of 22 EU Member States (MS) and 3 Associated Countries (AC), as well as 26 project partners and 14 Associated partners.

Adding the plus sign to the title of the previous GENDERACTION project not only indicates that it is a follow-up project but also makes it explicit that this project also addresses diversity and intersectionality (the gender+ approach).

Specifically, the GENDERACTIONplus project aims to:

- Develop strategic policy advice on existing and emerging policy solutions;
- Enhance the policy-making process by engaging with stakeholders, civil society organisations, and citizens;
- Build capacities, competence, and expertise for GE and mainstreaming in Research & Innovation among the policy and RFO community members, with special attention to countries with less comprehensive policies;
- Create impact through communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Thematically, the project focuses on:

- Intersectionality and inclusiveness
- Gender-based violence
- The gender dimension in research and innovation
- Monitoring and evaluating GE actions in the ERA
- Promoting institutional change through Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

GENDERACTIONplus aims to achieve the following impacts:

- Advance policy coordination among MS and AC through stakeholder and citizen engagement.
- Improve research careers and working conditions in European R&I, by developing policy dialogue and solutions on inclusion and intersectionality, combatting gender-based violence, and promoting institutional changes through GEPs.
- Improve research quality and the social responsibility of knowledge by integrating the gender dimension into research and innovation (R&I).
- Reduce geographic inequality by targeting less experienced/engaged countries and regions.

1.2. Objectives of the report

The main objective is to develop a template on ending gender-based violence for ERA RFOs. By moving partly beyond the results of the GENDERACTIONplus D3.1 and D3.2, as well as building further on the UniSAFE project deliverables and work in the GenderSAFE project, the objective is also to operationalise research-based knowledge on preventive strategies for ending gender-based violence. Further, an important objective is to align closely with the currently proposed ERA Zero-Tolerance Approach (ZTA) Code of Conduct (CoC) on ending gender-based violence, especially by incorporating its main principles and suggested actions in the logic and structure of the template. Finally, an important objective is to develop suggestions on how RFOs can move beyond their perceived responsibilities, especially by challenging normative assumptions on which organisations are eligible to act on instances of gender-based violence or able to give support to victims and survivors.

The deliverable consists of a text template for further development. The anticipated online version of the template is still to be developed. It was initially framed as a part of the objective for this deliverable. Due to the production of the ERA ZTA CoC on gender-based violence in parallel to the work in WP3 and T3.3, the content and logic of D3.3 had to be revised to a certain extent to fit the upcoming requirements of the ERA ZTA CoC. Both the GRC (Global Research Council) and the ERC (European Research Council) have been approached as potential platforms to host and continuously develop an online template for RFOs, but as yet this has not been settled finally. The aim is to pursue this end through the development of concrete policy advice together with FECYT and the GENDERACTIONPlus RFO CoP.

1.3. The relationship of this report to other tasks and work packages

This report mainly operationalises results and key recommendations in GENDERACTIONplus D3.1 and D3.2. There is a direct relationship to the work on GEP implementation and monitoring in WP6, as D3.3 suggest pragmatic ways for RFOs to structure their work on ending gender-based violence, not the least as it is foreseen to be included as a mandatory requirement in GEPs. There are also interlinkages with WP2 and WP7, through incorporating intersectional analysis and bringing knowledge on gender-based violence to capacity building in WP7. Experiences and ideas on ending gender-based violence as RFOs will also have an impact on the development of National Impact Plans (NIPs) and an EU impact plan through the work in WP8. Also, there is an indirect linkage with WP4 on policy development on the gender dimension in research, as several aspects of RFOs strategies for ending gender-based violence in research are of relevance for policy advice in this respect.

1.4. Structure of the report

The report starts with a description of background knowledge used when developing the template. It is a methods section with short presentations of different projects, deliverables and sources used. Then a section follows describing the relevant policy context on the current state on ending gender-based violence in the ERA, especially describing the ERA ZTA CoC and the RELIEF model developed within the GENDERACTIONplus project. The main part of the deliverable consists of a step-to-step template targeting ERA RFOs, with detailed descriptions on strategies and actions. Finally, some concluding remarks and a list of references end the deliverable.

2. METHODS FOR CREATING A RFO TEMPLATE

This section summarises the methods used for data collection and analysis in D3.3.

2.1. Revisiting results in the research review from task 3.1, focusing on RFOs

The results from the research review in task 3.1 focusing on RFOs, but also beyond, is important information when formulating the template document and hence has been analysed in relation to other empirical data. The template is also informed by the results of a large-scale systematic review on preventive methods on SH (Bondestam & Lundqvist 2020b), which are incorporated here in relation to other empirical data.

2.2. Analysing benchmark survey results focusing on RFOs

Detailed responses on specific measures and strategies, as reported by participating RFOs in the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey, have played an important role in setting the level of ambition in the template.

2.3 Engaging key stakeholders

To ensure stakeholder engagement, as a vital part of co-constructing knowledge on gender-based violence, WP3 has worked with the RFO CoP in GENDERACTIONplus through participating in several meetings and discussions. Further, during the work on D3.2, several other stakeholder dialogues have taken place, foremost with RFOs external to the GENDERACTIONplus CoP such as the NSF (National Science Foundation), GRC, ERC, and the Swedish RFOs Formas and Forte.

2.4. The RELIEF model

In cooperation with different stakeholders, WP3 has formulated a draft model for RFOs to work on ending gender-based violence in R&I – the RELIEF model (see section 3.3). The model builds on input and experiences of supporting RFOs on gender mainstreaming in Sweden during 2013-2023. Further to this, it is the outcome of developing measures and strategies for eradicating gender-based violence in RPOs in the context of different past and ongoing EU-funded projects. It is also a result of trying to map and analyse the lack of policies and research in ERA RFOs through D3.1 in the GENDERACTIONplus project. Ideas for developing this model have also emerged from years of international cooperation on RFOs' work on gender equality with stakeholders in the EU and globally.

2.5. MLW on gender-based violence with RFOs

A MLW was held on the 14th-15th of Sep 2023 in Milan. The aim of the MLW was to improve the understanding and knowledge on gender-based violence prevention among participants from different RFOs. Further, the aim was also to develop practices based on case studies and a discussion on the RELIEF model, as well as discussion and development of the UniSAFE draft fact sheet recommendations for RFOs in eradicating gender-based violence based on the 7P model. All RFO CoP members were invited to the MLW, together with the NSF, a visiting partner from the US. 23 participants from 10 RFOs and several other policy-making organisations involved in the GENDERACTIONplus project attended the workshop. The results from the MLW have been vital as input to developing the template for RFOs in this report.

2.6. ERA Forum Subgroup EU baseline strategy for a zero-tolerance Code of Conduct on ending gender-based violence and SH in ERA

The recent development of the ERA ZTA CoC for ending gender-based violence and SH has played a crucial role in setting the logic and structure of the template (EC, 2024). Not the least, the strong focus on commitment, action and accountability has been used a guiding principle throughout the template.

3. LOGIC AND STRUCTURE OF THE TEMPLATE

3.1. Policy background

The prevalence of gender-based violence in the ERA is high, as two out of three respondents to the UniSAFE survey have experienced some form of gender-based violence since they started at their institution (Lipinsky et al, 2022). This endemic of violence and abuse is also well documented in other research (Anitha & Lewis, 2018) and described in recent policy conclusions (Ljubljana Declaration, 2021; Call for Action, 2022; EC, 2024). The consequences of being exposed to gender-based violence are far-reaching and long-term, including stress, depression, anxiety, alcohol abuse, lack of motivation, increased tendency to interrupt studies or leave work, deteriorating mental and physical health, as well as impeding participation and perceptions of safety in the study and work environment in general (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020a; McDonald, 2012; Selkie et al, 2015). Specific groups at risk of gender-based violence, due to intersections of gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, age, and other factors, experience more severe and qualitatively different consequences from exposure to gender-based violence (Fedin, Holmes & Backes, 2018; Ong, 2005). The concept of gender-based violence in this report is inclusive, meaning SH is seen as one of many specific forms of gendered violence included in the umbrella concept of gender-based violence (Strid et al, 2021).

The current state of research knowledge on ending gender-based violence, as well as the adoption of targeted actions on an institutional level, are progressing slowly in the ERA (Bondestam, Lundqvist & Young Håkansson, 2023a). Analyses of recent policy developments clearly illustrate a seemingly random progress in several EU Member States, also with examples of both possible and factual setbacks in some national contexts (Bondestam, Lundqvist & Young Håkansson, 2023b; Fajmonová et al, 2021; SWG GRI, 2020). Further, research evidence on preventive methods decreasing the level of prevalence of gender-based violence is scarce (Bondestam & Lundqvist, 2020b; Vladutiu, Martin & Macy, 2011). Several gaps and inconsistencies in the current ERA policy framework are also identified (Call for Action, 2022; Ljubljana Declaration, 2021; EC, 2024) and point at the urgent need to move forward by suggesting concrete measures for ending gender-based violence for different stakeholders, including RFOs targeted in this deliverable. The recommendations from the GENDERACTIONplus D.3.2. suggest a holistic framework for addressing gender-based violence in ERA institutions, as displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Infrastructure on ending gender-based violence, extracted from GENDERACTIONplus D3.2.

As is visible in Figure 1, the ERA ZTA CoC is the overarching umbrella for all the other parts, of which the RELIEF model especially addresses the current RFO internal procedures and mechanisms relevant to engaging in ending gender-based violence. For further descriptions of the content of Figure 1, please read further in the GENDERACTIONplus D3.2 (Bondestam, Lundqvist & Young Håkansson, 2023b). The 7P framework is also part of the suggested template for RFOs, to differentiate the different areas of necessary action. The constituents of the 7Ps framework are not further described in this specific context, please visit the UniSAFE project website (<https://unisafe-gbv.eu/>) and further sources on the 7Ps model (Mergaert et al 2023).

3.2. The ERA Code of Conduct

An important background and input to the suggested template for RFOs is the currently developed *Proposed EU Baseline on a Strategy for a Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct to counteract gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in the EU Research and Innovation System*, here referred to as the ERA ZTA CoC (EC, 2024). A main credo of the ERA ZTA CoC is:

not tolerating any form of gender-based violence in higher education institutions and research institutions. Because gender-based violence is a continuum, the zero-tolerance approach focuses on capturing the entire spectrum of unacceptable behaviours from the less visible instances onwards, in order to cultivate an institutional culture in which there is no form of gender discrimination (EC, 2024, p. 10).

The ERA ZTA CoC mainly consists of three pillars, or baseline principles, guiding ERA institutions on how to frame measures and actions. These pillars thus constitute the main structure of the CoC and are also the guiding principles for the suggested template in D3.3. The pillars are described as follows:

- *Commitment.* Acknowledge the existence and systemic nature of gender-based violence in research and innovation institutions and the responsibility of institutions to proactively create safe and inclusive working and studying environments.
- *Action.* All stakeholders in the ERA must take concrete actions to turn the commitment to creating safe and inclusive research and innovation environments into the lived reality of researchers and students.
- *Accountability.* Establishing an appropriate institutional accountability mechanism to address all forms of gender-based violence, handle cases and implement restorative measures for victims.

What is crucial in this context concerning the pillars is the logic in relation to RFOs. *Commitment* means, translated to the RFO context, acknowledging gender-based violence as an intrinsic part of all instances of research funding and innovation processes and procedures. *Action* aims at RFOs full responsibility to ensure safe and inclusive conditions for all funded research and innovation. Finally, *accountability* targets RFOs institutional responsibility to ensure that all forms of violations and abuse are addressed, including taking part in and/or responsibility for handling cases and developing and implementing measures for restorative justice for victims and survivors. In this sense, the ERA ZTA CoC is clearly new and bold in its demand on all RFOs (as well as for all the other ERA stakeholders) *to shift the perception* of their role in ending gender-based violence in research and innovation. The three principles in the ERA ZTA CoC also have several specified measures defined and declared in more detail which will be instrumental for enhancing ERA stakeholder commitment and action further.

3.3. The RELIEF model

A specific challenge for RFOs, when working towards ending gender-based violence, is the understanding of the reach and responsibility of the institution as such. This was evident during the Milan MLW held in September 2023 together with different RFO stakeholders. Several arguments were put forward as to why RFOs have a limited possibility to contribute with measures for ending gender-based violence in RPOs. RFOs' general inability to advance beyond a given legal and/or national (and international) context, lack of resources and competencies, being unable to engage with incidents of gender-based violence in RPOs as they are not employers of researchers in most instances, and so forth. A key development from GENDERACTIONplus D3.2. was to attempt to counteract this narrative of RFOs inability to end gender-based violence in RPOs, by introducing ideas on how to use *already existing internal processes* of RFOs as a way forward. This was then developed into a specific set of principles and actions, termed the RELIEF model. This model consists of six different parts, which are (cf Bondestam, Lundqvist & Young Håkansson, 2023b, for more details):

Role clarity: RFOs redefining themselves as key actors in ending gender-based violence.

Ethical governance: Using ethical statutes on research misconduct as a way of inhibiting perpetrator behaviour and cultures in RPOs.

Legal framework: Supplementary actions taken by RFOs beyond legal boundaries, such as withdrawing or withholding funding, setting up whistleblowing systems, building support structures.

Internal procedures: Mainstreaming gender-based violence notions throughout the funding process, including RPOs to declare there are no ongoing processes or cases of gender-based violence in the name of an applicant.

Evaluation and monitoring: Integrating notions of gender-based violence in already existing evaluation and monitoring mechanisms in the funding system.

Funding: Proactive approach on funding research on gender-based violence.

These different parts of the RELIEF model largely resonate with the proposed ERA ZTA CoC. The latter is set to instruct the logic and structure of the template as a cross-cutting mechanism, meaning the three different pillars are set as steps to address each proposed part of the RELIEF model.

4. A TEMPLATE FOR RFOs

In this section, a template is set as a script through which RFOs, by using a step-by-step approach, can define, develop, and design their commitment to ending gender-based violence as an institution. As the current situation in the ERA suggest different levels of knowledge, expertise, resources, and engagement in ending gender-based violence among EU MS, it is important to recognize the possibility to at least cover the main RELIEF model parts of the template, as these still are generic for all RFOs in the ERA. The level of commitment, action and accountability will, nonetheless, vary accordingly.

As RFOs are setting up their work on ending gender-based violence, the template can support the development of a solid, institutional framework on ending gender-based violence, in line with recent research arguing for the need to create intra-institutional, sustainable structures for ending gender-based violence in a long-term perspective (Bondestam, 2024). For each step in the template, an overall description introduces the key focus. Then the ERA ZTA CoC pillars are brought in to clarify the different aspects of each step, also suggesting which main parts will be necessary to focus on, develop and sometimes redefine.

4.1. STEP 1: Role clarity

The first step is perhaps the most important in this template on which further proposed strategies and actions are dependent. In sum, it entails shifting the perception of a RFO in line with the ERA ZTA CoC, meaning defining the RFO as a key actor in ending gender-based violence in RPOs. The opposite will run the risk of funding violence and abuse through an involuntary ignorance of how gender-based violence effects the terms of doing research, and thus the possibilities for applying for funding in the first place.

4.1.2. Commitment

Redefine the RFO as an institution with a commitment to end gender-based violence in RPOs, insisting on creating safe and respectful terms for doing research equals quality of research output. Key arguments and examples as to why this is necessary and how it can be operationalised in terms of concrete actions are well defined in the UniSAFE recommendations for RFOs (UniSAFE, 2023).

4.1.2. Action

Develop and implement an institutional CoC on ending gender-based violence which resonates directly with the ERA ZTA CoC (EC, 2024). Depending on the national context and the current situation in the national R&I system, it might not be possible to include all of the identified necessary parts of each pillar in the ERA CoC, but these are preferably used as the starting point for identifying core parts of the institutional CoC.

4.1.3. Accountability

Set up procedures for internal accountability on accepting and respecting the internal CoC on gender-based violence. Also define possible sanctions for staff not complying with the CoC, in breach of the rules for internal and external commitment.

4.2. STEP 2: Ethical governance

Gender-based violence in R&I in the ERA is made possible partly through funding processes. Research funding and innovation enables researchers to misuse their economic and academic power, executing violent and abusive behaviours and other actions falling under the definition of gender-based violence. One way of addressing this, from the viewpoint of RFOs, is to specifically address gender-based violence as a breach of the core principles of ethics in research.

4.2.1. Commitment

RFOs are obliged to commit to research-based knowledge on the existence of gender-based violence in R&I, and one crucial way to do this is by identifying gender-based violence as one of several forms of unethical research behaviour. Preferably, RFOs can commit to this stance by including gender-based violence as an integral part of the core ethical definition of research misconduct.

4.2.2. Action

Define gender-based violence as a concept in relation to other core concepts in definitions of research misconduct, preferably by incorporating the UniSAFE theoretical definitions (Strid et al, 2021). Also make sure to include the definition of gender-based violence in the current criteria for detecting research misconduct within the RFO. Align all existing policies, protocols, and other institutional measures, so they all include gender-based violence in this sense. Make sure gender-based violence as a form of research misconduct is included in Step 5 in the template, as part of evaluation and monitoring of research funding.

4.2.3. Accountability

Define how both perpetrator and institutional accountability will unfold if research misconduct in terms of gender-based violence is detected. This might imply the same effects as already existing procedures and penalties for research misconduct, but it is important to also include possible sanctions in legal terms as some forms of gender-based violence are defined as criminal acts by other laws than usually deployed in legal cases of research misconduct.

4.3. STEP 3: Legal framework

One crucial result from the work done in GENDERACTIONplus D3.1. and D3.2. is identifying a tendency of RFOs to define their possibilities to act on potential and actual incidents of gender-based violence as legally difficult. RFOs are not the employer of researchers, and do not impose juridical sanctions. Therefore, other possible actions are important to pursue.

4.3.1. Commitment

Commit to develop strategies and measures, as a part of the institutional framework for ending gender-based violence in RPOs, which are complementary to employer responsibilities of RPOs as well as legal frameworks in the national context.

4.3.2. Action

Identify all possible actions, following the stated commitment in 4.3.1, such as for example withdrawing or withholding funding, setting up whistleblowing systems, independent investigative functions on formal reports, building support structures for victims and survivors external to RPOs, giving other targeted provision of services outside the RPO context, etc. Use the different recommendations stated in research and policy for this part (cf EC, 2024; UniSAFE, 2023; Strid et al, 2021).

4.2.3. Accountability

Identify all possible sanctions, both economic and academic, which might be put to use by the RFO beyond its current internal procedures. At this point, there are few examples of such mechanisms in use in the ERA (Bondestam, Lundqvist & Young Håkansson, 2023b). Therefore, it is suggested to create stakeholder partnerships especially with RPOs and national authorities, to find the best complementary measures possible. It will also be important to ensure such measures do not intrude with the sovereignty of RPOs or impede on core principles of academic and institutional freedom.

4.4. STEP 4: Internal procedures

In this step it is important to identify relevant internal procedures enabling the former parts of the template, that is operationalising the shift in role clarity, making sure ethical governance protocols include gender-based violence as part of research misconduct, and addressing key actions beyond legal frameworks in the national context.

4.4.1. Commitment

Identify all possible key factors in an institutional framework as set by current research (Bondestam, 2024). Preferably use the existing assessment framework for developing an understanding of the drivers for institutional change, as defined in recent output from the UniSAFE project (Strid et al, 2022).

4.4.2. Action

The main *action* will be to foster an implementation process for the institutional CoC.

Further, acknowledge a research-based understanding of how long-term change in institutions, regarding counteracting gender-based violence, depends on the way gender mainstreaming integrates measures and strategies for ending gender-based violence (Bondestam, 2024). Therefore, most important in this regard is to secure an effective, well resourced, and sustained internal organisation for gender mainstreaming of research funding and innovation processes. This, in turn, includes three interlinked change management initiatives:

1. secure gender perspectives in every step of the funding process, from proposing calls and receiving applications to the process of peer-review and decision-making.
2. enable funding processes actively supporting the inclusion of a gender dimension in research and innovation.
3. implement gender-based violence as an integrated part of gender mainstreaming of research funding and innovation processes, making it one of several core aspects of the concept of quality in research output.

Finally, this will also imply several different strategies for internal change management, including revising current policies on gender-based violence and GE, training and capacity building of key staff responsible for administrating research funding and innovation processes, and in other ways striving towards fulfilling the necessary conditions identified in ending gender-based violence through the 7Ps framework.

4.4.3. Accountability

Identify possible, internal RFO mechanisms to ensure holding RPOs and researchers applying for funding *accountable* for past, ongoing (and avoiding the potential risk of future) violations and abuse. This entails at least three different parts:

1. Setting up contracts for researchers and/or institutions applying for funding in which they must declare consent with not being part of any ongoing processes of gender-based violence, including unresolved reported violations and/or legal cases of gender-based violence.
2. Setting up a funding mechanism which implies the refusal of being part of any funding process if the first condition of consent is not fulfilled.
3. Setting up a funding mechanism which implies withdrawal or withholding of an already funded research budget if a breach of the first condition of consent is identified. In this case it is of utmost importance to ensure research funding and innovation is not withdrawn or withheld from potential and actual victims of gender-based violence, including bystanders, due to for example being part of a research group led by a principal investigator being the accused perpetrator.

4.5. STEP 5: Evaluation and monitoring

There is a need to foster long-term commitment of compliance to both the ERA CoC and the RFO's internal CoC. This is achieved through a consistent system for monitoring and evaluation. It is strongly recommended *not* to develop a specific system for this purpose, rather to integrate gender-based violence as a core part of already existing strategies and procedures for monitoring and evaluation of research funding and innovation. In this way, both institutional sustainability and relevant measures can be set.

4.5.1. Commitment

Commit to include and integrate gender-based violence as one criterion for ongoing monitoring and evaluation of research funding and innovation.

4.5.2. Action

Use step 2 and 3 in the template to set the monitoring and evaluation criteria in external research funding and innovation. Also include all parts of step 4 in the template for the purpose of internal monitoring.

4.5.3. Accountability

Define clear criteria for sanctions to use when evaluation and monitoring detects any form of breach of the funding contract concerning gender-based violence and align with the suggested parts in 4.4.3 in the template.

4.6. STEP 6: Funding

A recurring result and recommendation from several EU funded projects, policy advice and other reports on gender-based violence in the ERA is an identified lack of relevant research on gender-based violence (for example Ljubljana Declaration, 2021; Call for Action, 2022; SWG GRI 2020; UniSAFE, 2023). This includes both research on gender-based violence and R&I in general, and research targeting methods, strategies, and resources for ending gender-based violence on the institutional level.

4.2.1. Commitment

Commit to fund research on gender-based violence as a part of the institutional CoC.

4.2.2. Action

There are several ways RFOs can strengthen funding of research on gender-based violence:

- Invite researchers to identify priority topics for research on gender-based violence in R&I
- Include gender-based violence as a priority topic in existing and future funding schemes and programs
- Engage national stakeholders in prioritising funding on gender-based violence in R&I

4.2.3. Accountability

Aim for attracting research on the topic of gender-based violence in research and allocate a specific budget for this if relevant. Align with the protocols, criteria, and mechanisms used for monitoring and evaluation of research funding as described in step 5 of the template.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Research funding and innovation sets the bedrock for science and education to strive towards excellence. But there is no excellence in science if research resides on potential and actual experiences of gender-based violence. In collaboration with other R&I stakeholders in their national contexts, RFOs have the possibility to exert a vital impact on ending gender-based violence in the ERA. An important insight for RFOs, as a starting point, is realising the extent to which they can act for safe and respectful research in RPOs through a variety of measures and strategies. By acknowledging the responsibility to ensure research funding and innovation is not supporting potential perpetrators of gender-based violence, RFOs will contribute directly to protecting potential victims and, because of this, will foster high quality in research and education.

In this deliverable, a logic for ending gender-based violence, through already existing internal procedures and competencies within ERA RFOs, is developed in detail. The advantage of this approach is obvious. RFOs do not have to wait for legal amendments, economic resources or other capacities – they can start out implementing the proposed strategies and activities right away. Adapting to a responsible role in this sense as an RFO, the next steps will be to use the current mechanisms of evaluation and monitoring to set sanctions on perpetrators and institutions not complying to the ERA ZTA CoC. Further, incorporating gender-based violence as a criterion for defining research misconduct will have an immense importance, as it explicitly sets gender-based violence as an intrinsic part of ethics when doing research. Finally, ensuring funding is not enhancing toxic and abusive researchers is key for change, as both research and experience clearly shows the vast consequences of a laissez-faire approach to gender-based violence.

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7. REFERENCES

- Anitha, S., & Lewis, R. (2018). *Gender Based Violence in University Communities. Policy, Prevention and Educational Initiatives*. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Bondestam, F. (2024). Addressing Gender-Based Violence through the ERA Policy Framework: A Systemic Solution to Dilemmas and Contestations for Institutions. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 13(2), 74–99. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v13n2p74>.
- Bondestam, F., & Lundqvist, M. (2020a). *Efforts to Prevent Sexual Harassment in Academia. An International Research Review*. Stockholm: Swedish Council for Higher Education. https://www.uhr.se/globalassets/_uhr.se/publikationer/2020/uhr-efforts-to-prevent-sexual-harassment-in-academia.pdf.
- Bondestam, F., & Lundqvist, M. (2020b). Sexual Harassment in Higher Education – A Systematic Review. *European Journal of Higher Education*, 10(4), 397-419. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568235.2020.1729833>.
- Bondestam, F., Lundqvist, M., & Young Håkansson, S. (2023a). *GENDERACTION plus D3.1 Benchmarking Report on GBV and SH Targeting National Authorities and RFOs*. https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/101058093_GENDERACTIONplus_D3.1_Benchmarking-report-on-GBV-and-SH-targeting-national-authorities-and-RFOs.pdf.
- Bondestam, F., Lundqvist, M., & Young Håkansson, S. (2023b). *GENDERACTION plus D3.2 Baseline Document on Current and Future RFO Preventive Measures on GBV and SH*. https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/GENDERACTIONplus_D3.2_Baseline-document-on-current-and-future-RFO-preventive-measures-on-GBV-and-SH.pdf.
- Call for Action (2022). *Working towards Safe and Respectful Higher Education and Research for All. Call for Action to End Gender Based Violence*. https://genderaction.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Call-for-Action_GBV-2022_final.pdf
- Council of Europe. (2014). *Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence* (Council of Europe Treaty Series No 210). Istanbul: Council of Europe.
- EC. (2020). *A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025*.
- EC. (2024, forthc.). *Proposed EU Baseline on a Strategy for a Zero-Tolerance Code of Conduct to counteract gender-based violence, including sexual harassment, in the EU Research and Innovation System*.
- Fajmonová, V., Huck, A., Andreska, Z., Dvořáčková, J., Linková, M., Struzińska, K., ... Wuiame, N. (2021). *UniSAFE D3.2 Report on the European Policy Baseline*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5780037>.
- Lipinsky, A., Schredl, C., Baumann, H., Humbert, A., & Tanwar, J. (2022). *Gender-Based Violence and its Consequences in European Academia. Summary Results from the UniSAFE Survey*. https://unisafe-gbv.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/UniSAFE-survey_prevalence-results_2022.pdf.
- Ljubljana Declaration. (2021). *Gender Equality in Research and Innovation*. https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MIZS/Dokumenti/PSEU/Ljubljana-Declaration-on-Gender-Equality-in-Research-and-Innovation- endorsed_final.pdf.

- McDonald, P. (2012). Workplace Sexual Harassment 30 Years On: A Review of the Literature. *International Journal of Management Reviews: IJMR*, 14(1),1-17.
- Mergaert, L., Linková, M., & Strid S. (2023). Theorising Gender-Based Violence Policies: A 7P Framework. *Social Sciences*, 12(7), 385. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci12070385>.
- Ong, M. (2005). Body Projects of Young Women of Color in Physics: Intersections of Gender, Race, and Science. *Social Problems*, 52, 593-617.
- Selkie, E. M., Kota, R., Chan, Y.-F., & Moreno, M. (2015). Cyberbullying, Depression, and Problem Alcohol Use in Female College Students: A Multisite Study. *Cyberpsychology Behavior and Social Networking*, 18, 79-86. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2014.0371>.
- Strid, S., Humbert, A. L., Hearn, J., Bondestam, F., & Husu, L. (2021). *UniSAFE D3.1 Theoretical and conceptual framework*. [UniSAFE D3.1 Theoretical and conceptual framework \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/record/5044441).
- Strid, S., Bondestam, F., Humbert, A. L., Tzanakou, C., & Mergaert, L. (2023). *UniSAFE D6.2 Assessment Framework to Take Stock, Measure Progress, and Identify Strengths and Weaknesses in Organisational Responses to Gender-Based Violence along the 7Ps*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10199913>.
- SWG GRI (Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation). (2020). *Sexual Harassment in the Research and Higher Education Sector: National Policies and Measures in EU Member States and Associated Countries*. Brussels: ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation.
- UniSAFE. (2023). *Recommendations for Research Funding Organisations towards Ending Gender-Based Violence*. Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8383082>.
- Vladutiu, C. J., Martin, S. L., & Macy, R. J. (2011). College- or University-Based Sexual Assault Prevention Programs: A Review of Program Outcomes. *Trauma Violence & Abuse*, 12, 67-86.

